

O‘SMIRLARDA DESTRUKTIV XULQ-ATVOR KO‘RINISHLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada voyaga yetmagan o‘smir yoshdagi o‘quvchilarda dunyo bo‘ylab tarqalgan destruktiv xulq-atvor ko‘rinishlarini shakllanishi hamda ularga to‘g‘ri diagnost qo‘yish, ular korreksiya ishlarini olib boorish bo‘yicha ma’lumotlar bayon etilgan.

***Kalit so‘zlar:** destruktiv xulq, buzg‘unchi faoliyat, disfunktsional oila, ijtimoiy ta’sir, shaxs, ong va ongsizlik.*

ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ДЕСТРУКТИВНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ У ПОДРОСТКОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье изложена информация о формировании у несовершеннолетних подростков всемирно распространенных проявлений деструктивного поведения, а также о постановке им правильного диагноза, проведении коррекционной работы.

Ключевые слова: деструктивное поведение, деструктивная деятельность, дисфункциональная семья, социальное влияние, личность, сознание и бессознательное.

DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIORAL MANIFESTATIONS IN ADOLESCENTS

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ANNOTATION

This article describes the formation of destructive behavioural patterns in underage adolescent learners worldwide, as well as the correct diagnosis of them, which they carry out corrective work.

Keywords: *destructive behavior, disruptive activity, dysfunctional family, social influence, personality, mind and unconsciousness.*

Introduction

By the middle of the 20th century, the problem of destructive behavior began to take shape. The psychological approach was focused on the separation of socio-psychological disparity of individual manifestations in the destructive behavior of adolescent students. Destructive behavior is a behavior pattern directed towards negating any alternative thoughts that contradict the social behavior patterns perceived in society. Destructive behavior, on the other hand, is verbal or other manifestations of internal activity aimed at destroying something. Elimination covers all areas of personality: socialization, health, relationships are important people. Such behavior leads to a deterioration in the quality of the presence of an individual, a decrease in

critical attitude to one's own actions, cognitive disturbances in the perception and interpretation of what is happening, a decrease in self-esteem and emotional disorders.

This often leads to social adaptation, up to the absolute isolation of the individual. Such behavior is sometimes the result of a defense mechanism that consists of detecting an aggressor. The considered change in behavior is characterized by a deviation from the norms of behavior and morality adopted by society.

It is common to divide behavioral patterns into disruptive or abnormal behaviors and constructive (normal), generally accepted behaviors. Abnormal behavior that forms destructively is characterized by non-standard, Pathology-Limited, dissatisfaction with society. This is often a deviation from the point of view of social guidelines, medical norms, psychological attitudes.

Literature analysis

Each model of behavior is formed in childhood. A four-to five-year-old baby studies the information that determines his further relationship with the social environment. A full-fledged family, dominated by mutual understanding, care, attention, love has a beneficial effect on the maturation of the psyche of babies, laying the foundation for patterns of behavior. Therefore, individuals who do not receive adequate education, warmth, attention, love fall into the category of danger.

You should also know that children often take a pattern of destructive behavior from their parents.

Scientists have found that the destructive behavior of an individual is successfully formed against the background of the presence of the following factors:

- the presence of many social deviations (bureaucracy, corruption, drunkenness, crime);
- liberalization of measures of social influence (body, lowering the level of criticism);
- situation anomalies(speculation, fictitious marriages;
- weakening measures to combat abnormal behavior (lack of fines, punishment systems).

Freud was convinced that destructive behavior was the result of a person's negative attitude towards their own person. He also noted that the crash was one of the main drivers. Proponents of psychoanalytic theory have argued that supernatural actions are inherent to all subjects of a person to varying degrees, except that the objects of such actions (other personified or inanimate objects or his own) differ. Adler has a similar view, which he believes is the primary reason for disruptive behavior being a sense of alienation and non-existence.

Fromm argues that deviant behavior triggers an unrealized human potential, as well as failing to use effective energy for its own purpose. Durkheim made a social analysis of the variability of the behavioral response under consideration. While Merton wrote that the disruptive behavior anomie was related to a special moral and psychological state characterized by the collapse of a system of moral values and spiritual guidance, Worsley, in turn, explored the relativism of the relationship between sociocultural norms and "absolute" standards.

Research methodology

The problem of self-destruction of adolescents is very relevant, since it leads to addiction, suicide attempts by adolescents, alcoholism. Over the years, the number of children has been increasing. Cases of drug addiction, alcoholism of minors have long been not surprising to anyone. In addition, the described problems are observed not only in families in difficult situations. Statistical observations say that about 37% of children are treated for drug addiction medical institution registered, coming from much more prosperous families.

It is desirable that the parent's search for the cause of changes in adolescent behavior is based on a constructive solution to the problems that have arisen. If the family members of a teenager are regularly accustomed to solving their problems on the basis of interaction through conflicts, shouts, then in another social situation the teenager seeks to behave exactly like this; - personal problems (features of sexual development in adolescents that cause the origin of problems of a physiological and psychological nature – manifestation of the characteristics of the puberty period); – dissatisfaction with its appearance - "Terzite complex" (inadequate perception by

adults). The model of behavior comes from childhood and is primarily based on the pattern of parents.

Conclusion

In order to prevent the formation of desturative behavior in adolescent students and provide practical assistance to this, we must first determine the cause. That is, we need to know his environment, his relationship with his parents, Sagittarius, friends, his psychological state at the moment. Practical help should be provided to solve the child's problems by his parents, a teacher, a psychologist. Under any circumstances, a person should be strong-willed, not stop moving with enthusiasm, setting a goal for himself. First of all, I think that a person should be able to convince himself to achieve his goals. Because a person can only convince someone of what he believes in. There will be no people without abilities, but there will be lazy people.

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